

ESTIMATING STOCHASTIC FRONTIER MODEL FOR POULTRY INDUSTRY IN BANGLADESH: A FARM LEVEL ANALYSIS

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Abstract: *The study analyzed the technical efficiency of poultry farm both broiler meat and layer egg production in Bangladesh from a sample of 200 poultry farmers selected from Savar and Dhamrai Upazilla under Dhaka and Bajitpur and Kuliarchar Upazilla under Kishorganje district. Stochastic parametric technique was used to analyze the technical efficiency of poultry farmers. Results showed that among different input factors, doc size and feed input played crucial role in broiler output. Estimated mean technical efficiencies were 56% for broiler and 67% for layer farm respectively. The difference in the level of technical efficiency postulates the existence of further opportunities for farmers to escalate their productivity and income through enhancements in their technical efficiency. Different observed socioeconomic variables, which encompassed farming experience, age, education, family size, training, credit, extension contact and regular medication, were found to be negative and significantly related to technical inefficiency.*

Keywords: *Meat production, technical efficiency, frontier analysis, poultry farmers, Bangladesh*

JEL Code: *Q0, C10, C14, Q1, D58*

I. INTRODUCTION

The difficulty of food insecurity and hunger in contemporary years has sustained to depict the concentration of research experts and governments globally. As per as FAO (2015) availability, accessibility and sufficient quantity and quality of food are required to mean for food security in order to contribute towards human development. The most crucial concern in the global food basket crisis is protein, in particular of animal origin. Isika et al. (2006) suggested poultry production as a tactical resource of animal protein in human nutrition due to its shorter life cycle, likely for high productive capability, high rate of return and its proficiency in nutrient conversion to high class animal protein.

One of the vital challenge of Bangladesh agriculture is its capability to nourish the ever-increasing population with satisfactory food value i.e. calorie and protein. Poultry industry is one of the chief among livestock sub-sector that is devoted to supply cheap sources of good

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quality nutritious animal protein (Shamsuddoha, 2010). Poultry farming is a sub-sector of the Agriculture sector in Bangladesh. By far poultry is the leading livestock group containing generally of chickens, ducks and turkeys (FAO 2009). In total, poultry products (egg and meat) constitute 30% of all animal protein consumed worldwide (Permin A. et. al. 2005). That is poultry meat accounts for 30% of global meat consumption. In global meat production poultry meat is taking the second place after pork (FAO Corporate Document Repository, 2007).

The poultry is a crucial avenue in nurturing agricultural growth. Bangladesh poultry plays an important economic role for 73% of rural people who lives in rural areas (Reneta 2005). In 2020, per capita poultry meat consumption is anticipated to extent 8.42Kg, which is now nearly 4kg, while in Pakistan 5.5kg and in the U.S. over 50kg. as per as the World's Poultry Science Association Bangladesh Branch (Dhaka tribune, 2016). In the nineties total investment in the poultry sector was only Tk 15 hundred crore, but now it is more than Tk 15 thousand crore. This has created job opportunity for more than 60 lakh people (Ali et al. 2012)

The fisheries and livestock sectors are two chief pillars of our economy. Role of these two sectors to total GDP was 3.69 and 7.73 percent respectively (MoFL, 2016). They are also driving the country towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals that focuses on 'achieve food security and improved nutrition'. Poultry industry has the prospective to support Bangladesh reach the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of reducing malnutrition and ensuring better health for the countrymen. Among 17 SDGs, ending hunger, achieving food security and improving nutritional status are the ones that the poultry industry can deal with and pay much through providing protein items. (Dhaka Tribune, August 24, 2016)

According to Department of Livestock (DLS) about 6.5 percent of national GDP is covered by the livestock sector (Banglapedia). Annual growth rate of poultry is 15-18%. Contribution in GDP is 2.4% (BPSCC). About 38% of animal protein originates from poultry meat and egg (Layer Rearing Manual, 2010, BLRI). Table 1 below shows the contribution of sub sectors to GDP at a constant (2005/06) price. Although the share of the agriculture sector in GDP is declining in relative terms, in absolute terms the amount has increased considerably. In FY 2015-16 the role of agriculture was forecasted to be 11.67 percent. Growth of all subsector drops as compared to the last year.

Table 1: Contribution of Agriculture by Sub Sector to GDP (at percentage)

Sub Sector	Contribution of Agriculture to GDP in Percentage (GDP at Constant Price—Base Year 2005/06)								
	2007/08	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2011/12	2012/13	2013/14	2014/15	2015/16*
Crop	10.88	10.63	10.79	10.5	10.01	9.49	9.28	8.87	8.32
Livestock	2.19	2.13	2.06	1.98	1.9	1.84	1.78	1.73	1.66
Forestry	1.82	1.82	1.81	1.79	1.78	1.76	1.74	1.72	1.69
Total	14.89	14.58	14.66	14.27	13.69	13.09	12.8	12.32	11.67
Fisheries	3.79	3.78	3.73	3.73	3.68	3.68	3.69	3.69	3.65

Source: Bangladesh Economic Review, 2016, Table: 2.4; Page: 21

From the Table 2, we see that in FY 2016-17 the contribution of livestock sector in GDP at constant price was 1.60% and the rate of growth was 3.32%. This is a very positive sign that the growth rate of livestock contribution in national GDP is rising over the period of time.

With the annual growth rate of 7.65% (according to BBS based on last nine months from July 2016-March 2018) the growth rate of livestock is also supposed to rise gradually.

Table 2: Livestock Contribution in GDP

Indicators	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-2016	2016-2017p
GDP(Base:2005-06)**	2.06	1.98	1.9	1.84	1.78	1.73	1.66	1.60
Growth rate of GDP	2.51	2.59	2.68	2.74	2.83	3.1	3.21	3.32

**GDP calculated at constant price (Source: BBS); p denotes provisional; Prepared by Dr. Hossan Md. Salim, LE Section, DLS.

Source: DLS, 2017, Livestock Economy at a Glance 2016-17

Though the share of the animal farming in GDP is small, it keeps huge contribution towards meeting the requirements of daily essential animal protein. Table 3 shows the growth of the livestock and poultry population of the country over the past seventeen years. As can be seen from the table that number of livestock and poultry population rose to 53.59 million (535.90 lakh) and 304.1 million (3,041 lakh) respectively in FY 2013-14. Similarly, in FY 2014-15 (up to February) the population of livestock and poultry population rose to 53.97 million (539.72 lakh) and 312.2 million (3122.93 lakh) respectively. Finally it was 54.27 million (542 lakh) for livestock and 317.7 million (3177 lakh) for poultry respectively in FY 2015-16 (up to February). Finally, the population of livestock and poultry rose to 64.74 million (647 lakh) and 329.2 million (3292 lakh) respectively in FY2016-17.

Table 3: Number of Livestock and Poultry in Bangladesh (Number in Millions)

Year	Cattle	Buffalo	Goat	Sheep	Total (Livestock)	Chicken	Duck	Total (Poultry)
2000-01	22.39	0.92	16.27	2.11	41.69	142.68	33.83	176.51
2001-02	22.46	0.97	16.96	2.2	42.59	152.24	34.67	186.91
2002-03	22.58	1.01	17.69	2.29	43.57	162.44	35.54	197.98
2003-04	22.6	1.06	18.41	2.38	44.45	172.63	36.4	209.03
2004-05	22.67	1.11	19.16	2.47	45.41	183.45	37.28	220.73
2005-06	22.8	1.16	19.94	2.57	46.47	194.82	38.17	232.99
2006-07	22.87	1.21	20.75	2.68	47.51	206.89	39.08	245.97
2007-08	22.9	1.26	21.56	2.78	48.5	212.47	39.84	252.31
2008-09	22.97	1.31	22.4	2.87	49.55	221.39	41.23	262.62
2009-10	23.05	1.35	23.27	2.97	50.64	228.04	42.67	270.71
2010-11	23.12	1.39	24.14	3.02	51.67	234.68	44.12	278.8
2011-12	23.19	1.44	25.11	3.82	53.56	242.86	45.7	288.56
2012-13	23.24	1.45	25.11	3.12	53.2	249.6	47.23	296.23
2013-14	23.48	1.45	25.43	3.20	53.59	255.3	48.86	304.1
2014-15	23.63	1.46	25.60	3.27	53.97	261.7	50.52	312.2
2015-16*	23.73	1.46	25.71	3.31	54.27	266.07	51.62	317.7
2015-16*	23.73	1.46	25.71	3.31	54.27	266.07	51.62	317.7
2016-17	23.93	1.47	25.93	3.41	64.74	275.18	54.01	329.2

* indicates up to February, 2016

Source: Department of Livestock, Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock

Ref: Year 2001-2010: Bangladesh Economic Review 2012, Chp-7: Agriculture, Table: 5.10, page-50

Year 2011-2013: Bangladesh Economic Review 2013, Chp-7: Agriculture, Table: 6.11, page-69

Year 2014-2016: Bangladesh Economic Review 2016, Chp-7: Agriculture, Table: 7.8, page-93

Year 2016-2017: Bangladesh Economic Review 2017, Chp-7: Agriculture, Table: 7.8, page-110

The contribution of livestock and poultry in the national economy of Bangladesh was presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Contribution of Livestock and Poultry in the National Economy of Bangladesh

Particulars	Contribution
Contribution of Livestock in Gross Domestic Product (GDP), (2016-17)p	1.60%
GDP growth rate of Livestock (2016-17) p	3.32 %
GDP volume (Current price) in Crores (Taka), (2016-17) p	35,576
Share of Livestock in Agricultural GDP (2016-17) p	14.31%
Employment (Directly)	20%
Employment (Partly)	50%
Cultivation of land by livestock	50%
Fuel supply from livestock and poultry	25%

Source: DLS, 2017, Livestock Economy at a Glance 2016-17

It is also to be noted that livestock sector has been earning foreign currency by exporting meat and livestock products to USA, UAE, China, Kuwait, Canada, Japan and Maldives (Bangladesh Economic Review 2017, page 111)

Even with the poultry sector is an important part of our national economy, currently there has been no study that investigates the status of poultry sector from the efficiency perspective. In order to establish a sustainable poultry friendly plan for the country, it is essential to assess the sector in the gate up of efficiency analysis. Given the fact that Bangladesh is faced with different challenges as far as the livestock subsector is concerned, it then becomes crucial to quantitatively measure the existing level and determinants of efficiency and policy options available for swelling the current level of efficiency. The improvement in this sector can be sustained with a proper analysis of the technical efficiency (TE).

The measurement of farm efficiency is a central area of research both in the developed and developing world (Binuomote et al. 2008). Efficiency is an essential factor of productivity growth exclusively in developing agriculture where resources are scarce. Efficiency is an imperative economic concept used in assessing producers' performance to make sure that products are produced in the best and most profitable way (Park et al., 2010). Technical inefficiency (TE) is defined as the amount by which the level of production for the farm is less than the frontier output (Kibaara, 2005). The analysis of efficiency is generally associated with the possibility of farms producing a certain optimal stage of output from a certain level of resources or given level of output at least cost (Battese et al. 1995, Parikh A et Al. 1995). TE denotes to the ability of firms to employ the "best practice" in an industry so that not more than the required amount of a given set of inputs is used in producing the "best" level of output (Ajibefun, 2002 and Ohajianya 2006). A measure of producer performance is often worthwhile for policy purposes and the idea of economic efficiency provides a theoretical basis for such a measure (Alrwiset. Al., 2003)

However, an attempt has been made in order to tackle the issue. The specific objectives of this study were to estimate the determinants of: (i) poultry broiler farms output by estimating the elasticity of production of the inputs; and (ii) technical efficiency of table poultry broiler farms in Savar and Dhamrai Upazilla under Dhaka and Bajitpur and Kuliarchar Upazilla under Kishorganje district.

A good number of studies have been undertaken on different aspects of poultry and poultry farm in Bangladesh. The studies include production performance of poultry and demand for poultry (Talukder et al. 1982, Ukil 1994; Islam K.M. Nabiul 2001, Khan et. al. 2006, Rahman et al. 2009, Shah et al, 2011), measuring relative costs, returns and economic analyses (Miah 1990, Ahmed et al. 1995, Bhuiyan, 2003; Alam, 2004, Islam et al. 2016), benefit and profitability analysis of contract farming (Vukina and Foster, 1998, Begum I. A. et al 2000, Karim, 2000, Bairagi 2004 and Jabbar et. al. 2007), effectiveness of trained farmers (Ershad et al. 2004), marketing and value chain analysis (Rahman, 20004, USAID-ATDP 2005), role of NGO in poultry (Ahmed 2001, Shamsuddoha M. 2009), role of poultry in biogas and electricity generation (Zaman 2007, Sajib et. al. 2015, Alam 2017), environmental impact of the poultry sector in Bangladesh (Akter et al. 2004) etc.

However, those were quite descriptive in nature and suffered from lack of economic judgment analysis. The major effort of most of the previous works in Bangladesh was on the production, marketing, distribution aspect of poultry and such type of studies employed mainly simple cost benefit analysis. There have been some studies that have examined the efficiency of agricultural production in Bangladesh based on stochastic frontier (SFA) and data envelopment analysis (DEA) (Wadud and White, 2000, Kamruzzaman et al, 2006, Haider et al. 2011, Uddin et al. 2017) aiming on major food crops like rice, wheat, fish, maize etc. and no studies have dealt with the poultry. The efficiency analyses which have been done (Sarker et al., 1999; Effiong and Onyenweaku 2006) regarding poultry were not based on any of the above econometrical or statistical tools.

The present study differs from the previous study in Bangladesh by introducing the concept of efficiency considering variables that relate to both individual aspects and aspects of the decision-making process of the farmer in the form of well-known production function and stochastic analysis (SFA) which makes this paper unique for the Bangladesh context.

Two approaches are mainly available to estimate technical efficiency i.e. parametric and non-parametric. The parametric approach includes stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) while non-parametric approach includes the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method. DEA is known as sensitive approach to outliers (Hasnain et al., 2015). The main disadvantage of employing this mathematical technique is that it does not take into account other sources of statistical noise besides the inefficiency (Coelli et al, 2005). For that reason, we select the parametric technique (SFA). Parametric approach takes into account the stochastic noises of the data where the data envelopment analysis assumes there is no stochastic noise in the data (Abedullah, 2007)

II. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials and Methods

For the present study Savar and Dhamrai Upazilla under Dhaka district and Bajitpur and Kuliarchar Upazilla under Kishorganje district were selected. The data was collected through random selection of poultry farmers which gave the opportunity for fifty poultry farmers from each district making a total of 200 poultry farmers i.e. hundred farmers located in Dhaka and

the rest hundred from Kisharganj. Data collection was done by means of structured questionnaire and were analyzed using Stochastic Production Frontier Model. Stata 14 was applied to run the frontier model.

Dhaka Site Map

Kishorganje Site Map

2.2 Source of Data

Both primary and secondary data were used. The primary data was collected from farmers involved in the production of poultry broiler meat. Beside this, the study also employed information from different issues of Bangladesh Statistical Year Book published by Bureau of Statistics (BBS), Economic Review published by Finance Ministry and “Farm Poultry and Livestock Survey 2007-08” by BBS. About 115 poultry farmers were selected and after necessary correction 100 poultry farmers were finalized for our research study

2.3 The Analytical Framework

A production function is the functional relationship describing the maximum output that can be produced from a specific set of inputs, given the existing technology available to the firms involved.

A Stochastic Production Function is defined by

$$Y_i = F(X_i, B) \exp(V_i - U_i), \quad i = 1, 2 - n \quad (1)$$

Where Y_i is output of the i th farm, X_i is the vector of input quantities used by the i th farm, B is a vector of unknown parameters to be estimated, $f(.)$ represents an appropriate function (e.g., Cobb – Douglas, translog, etc). The term V_i is a symmetric error, which accounts for random variations in output due to factors beyond the control of the farmer e.g., weather, disease outbreaks, measurement errors etc, while the term U_i is a non-negative random variable representing inefficiency in production relative to the stochastic frontier. The random error V_i is expected to be independently and identically dispersed. The Stochastic Frontier model was independently proposed by Aigner et al., (1977) and Meeusen and Broeck (1977).

According to Battese and Coelli (1995), technical inefficiency effect is defined by

$$u_i = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_i Z_i + W_i$$

Where Z_i is a vector of explanatory variables associated with the technical inefficiency effects. δ_i is a vector of unknown parameter to be estimated. W_i is unobservable random variables, which are assumed to be identically distributed, obtained by truncation of the normal distribution with mean zero and unknown variance σ^2 , such that u_i is non-negative.

i. The Empirical Model

For this study, the production technology of poultry meat producers was assumed to be specified by the Cobb – Douglas frontier production function defined as follows:

$$Y = aX_1^{\beta_1} X_2^{\beta_2} X_3^{\beta_3} X_4^{\beta_4} X_5^{\beta_5} X_6^{\beta_6} X_7^{\beta_7} e^{V_1 - U_1} \quad (2)$$

$$Y = f(X_a ; B_i) e^E$$

Whereby:

Y= Quantity of meat or egg produced

X_a = A vector of input and other explanatory variable quantities

B_i = A vector of unknown parameter to be estimated

e = Error term

E = Stochastic disturbance term consisting of two independent elements which are U_i and V_i , where by $E = U_i + V_i$

U_i = One-sided efficiency component with a half normal distribution.

V_i = The non-negative unobservable random variable

The random error E represents random variations in the economic environment facing the production units, reflecting chance such as weather, disease outbreak and variable input quality, measurement errors, and omitted variables from the functional form (Aigner et al. 1977).

Cobb-Douglas production function model can be estimated using OLS (ordinary least square) method, in a linear form. The estimated equation was:

$$\ln Y_i = \ln a + b_1 \ln X_{1i} + b_2 \ln X_{2i} + b_3 \ln X_{3i} + b_4 \ln X_{4i} + b_5 \ln X_{5i} + (v_i - u_i) \quad (3)$$

$$\ln Y_i = b_0 + b_1 \ln X_{1i} + b_2 \ln X_{2i} + b_3 \ln X_{3i} + b_4 \ln X_{4i} + b_5 \ln X_{5i} + (v_i - u_i) \quad (4)$$

Where,

$\ln$ = the natural logarithm to base e

Y_i = Output of the poultry farmer per batch (total meat produced per batch in kg)

X_1 = Number of days worked in a year

X_2 = Size of Doc (number of birds per batch)

X_3 = Cost of feed per batch (in taka)

X_4 = Value of capital (in taka)

X_5 = Farm Area measured in decimal

v_i = random error assumed to be independent of u_i , identical and normally distributed with zero mean and constant variance $N(0, \sigma^2)$

U_i = Technical efficiency effect which are the result of behavior factors that could be controlled by an efficient management.

In equation 4 $\hat{a}_0$ is the intercept; U_i denotes the specific technical efficiency factor for farm i ; and v_i represents a random variable for farm i . The $\hat{a}$ coefficients are unknown parameters to be estimated, by the method of maximum likelihood, using the econometric package Stata version 14.

ii. Measuring Inefficiency Determinants

In addition to the general production model mentioned above, the efficiency model was also defined to estimate the impact of socioeconomic variables on the technical efficiencies of the broiler farmers. The model was defined by

$$U_i = Z_0 + d_1 \ln Z_1 + d_2 \ln Z_2 + d_3 \ln Z_3 + d_4 \ln Z_4 + d_5 \ln Z_5 + d_6 \ln Z_6 + d_7 \ln Z_7 + d_8 \ln Z_8 + d_9 \ln Z_9 + d_{10} Z_{10}$$

$$+d_{11}Z_{11}+d_{12}Z_{12}+d_{13}\ln Z_{13}+d_{14}\ln Z_{14}+W_i \quad (5)$$

Where

U_i = Technical (or economic) efficiency of the i th farmer already mentioned above

Z_1 = Years of farming experience in poultry production of the i th farmer

Z_2 = Age of the farmers (in years)

Z_3 = Level of formal Education (years of schooling)

Z_4 = Household size (family members in number)

Z_5 = Training on poultry (if Yes=1; No=0)

Z_6 = Access to credit facility (if Yes=1; No=0)

Z_7 = Meetings with extension agents/ respective govt. agencies per poultry production season (Yes=1;No=0)

Z_8 = Location of farm (Urban=1; Rural=0)

Z_9 =Types of poultry occupation

(1 = Poultry as main occupation and no other job

0 = Poultry as part time occupation and do other job also)

Z_{10} =Marital status (Married=1; Unmarried = 0)

Z_{11} =Membership of farmers Association/Cooperative society (Yes=1; No=0)

Z_{12} =Ownership of the farm (where Sole proprietor=0, Partnership=1

Z_{13} =Gender (if Female=1; Male=0)

Z_{14} =Regular Medication/Vaccination facilities (Yes=1; No=0)

Z_0 = Constant

W_i = Unobservable random variables

To determine the contributing factors to the observed technical efficiency, the above model was formulated and the δ coefficients are unknown parameters to be estimated.

III. RESULTS ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Descriptive Statistics of Broiler Farmers

In the study area, as per the Table 5, the mean flock size was 2567 birds. The average experience of farmers was 5.4 years. Farmers' average age was 40. The poultry farmer's average family members were 5.

TABLE 5: Broiler Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Flock size	100	2567.1	2559.238	100	1000
Experience	100	5.423	3.260286	1	15
Age	100	40.13	7.34662	18	54
Family members	100	5.03	1.714201	0	9

Source: Field survey, 2015

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF LAYER FARMERS

As per the Table 6, in the study area the mean flock size was 2467 birds. The average experience of farmers was 11 years. Farmers' average age was 42. The poultry farmer's average family members were 5.

Table 6: Layer Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Flock size	100	2435.8	2497.306	70	8500
Experience	100	11.423	5.494681	1	24
Age	100	42.05	9.020039	23	63
Family members	100	5.00	1.687745	0	8

Source: Field survey, 2015

3.2 Estimated Stochastic Frontier Production Function

The estimates for parameters of the Cobb-Douglas production function were shown in following tables. These parameters represented percentage change in the dependent variable as a result of percentage change in the independent variables, and as such show the relative position of these variables to meat productivity. Tables below show elasticity of production and Returns to Scale as well.

3.2.1 Frontier Function for Broiler

Labor input ($\ln X_1$) measured as man per days affected poultry production positively and significantly. As per the Table 7, labor input was observed significant at 1% level in the study area among broiler farmers indicating that labor activities were necessary to increase poultry output. Feeding and sorting activities constituting labor activities are required to achieve increased output in poultry production. Poultry production is labor intensive and the more attention farmers paid to the birds the higher the poultry output. Thus the 0.10 elasticity of labor suggests that a 1% increase in labor use would result to an increase of 0.10 percent in the farm output given that other inputs are constant.

DOC size ($\ln X_2$) was significant at 1% level and positive in sign as expected. This means that farmers who stock higher number of birds were producing more than those with smaller farm size. As the stock size increases, the space where the birds are housed is also expected to increase. The coefficient of **number of chicks** is 0.26 ($\ln X_2$) implying that one percent increase in the number of day old chicks will result in a 0.26 percent in the number of broilers produced per cycle given that other inputs are constant.

The estimated coefficient of **feed input** ($\ln X_3$) was positive and significant at 1% level. Feed appeared to be the most important production factor with the elasticity of 0.27 and was significant at the 1% level. This is in agreement with the concept of weight gain in broiler production and the physiology of feed conversion in poultry production. Broilers that are well fed gain weight faster attain marketable weights earlier and sold at higher unit prices. The more the appropriate feed fed to the birds at their various stages of development the more the farm reverence by more output. Thus the, 0.27 elasticity of feed suggests that a 1% increase in feed inputs, would result to an increase of 0.27 percent in the farm output.

Capital input ($\ln X_4$) variable was also significant and positive in sign. As more capital is invested in the poultry business, there is increased poultry production by farmers. Capital input significantly determines the output at 5% level in the study area. Thus the, 0.10 elasticity of feed suggests that a 1% increase in feed inputs, would result to an increase of 0.10 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **farm area** ($\ln X_5$) measured in decimal was positive, which conform to a priori expectation and was significant at 5% level. Output of poultry is majorly dependent on farm size. Therefore, the 0.07 elasticity of **farm size** implies that a 1% increase in farm size, *ceteris paribus*, would lead to an increase of 0.07 percent in the output of poultry broiler farmers holding *ceteris paribus* and vice versa.

Table 7: Cobb-Douglas Production Function for Broiler

Number of obs =	100			
F(5, 94)	= 80.466	R-squared = 0.812		
Prob > F	= 0.00	Adj R-squared = 0.791		
$\ln Y_{meat}$	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P>t
$\ln X_1$	0.109	0.023	4.696	8.76E-06
$\ln X_2$	0.264	0.085	3.090	0.002
$\ln X_3$	0.279	0.050	5.543	0.000
$\ln X_4$	0.100	0.046	2.176	0.032
$\ln X_5$	0.070	0.034	2.009	0.038
_cons	1.055	0.379	2.779	0.006
RTS	0.823			

Source: Author's Calculation from the Field Data

Note: Where, $\ln X_1$ = Labor input, $\ln X_2$ = DOC size, $\ln X_3$ = Feed input, $\ln X_4$ = Capital input and $\ln X_5$ = Area of farm

The RTS parameter of 0.823 was obtained from the summation of the coefficients of the estimated inputs involved in broiler production process which indicated that poultry-meat production in the study area was in the stage II of the production surface which by implication is within the rational zone for actors to operate. Thus, we can say a 1% increase in factor inputs would increase meat production by 0.823%.

3.2.2 Frontier Function for Layer

The coefficient of **labor input** employed ($\ln X_1$) in man per days was positive as expected and significant at 1% significance level. The more attention farmers paid to the birds the higher the poultry output. Thus the 0.09 elasticity of labor suggest that a 1% increase in labor use would result to an increase of 0.09 percent in the farm output given that other inputs are constant.

DOC size ($\ln X_2$) was significant at 1% level and positive in sign. This means that farmers who stock higher number of birds were producing more than those with smaller doc size. The coefficient of number of chicks is 0.26 implying that one percent increase in the number of day old chicks will result in a 0.26 percent in the number of broilers produced per cycle given that other inputs are constant.

The estimated coefficient for **feed input** ($\ln X_3$) was positive and statistically significant at 1% significant level. Feed is a central resource used in poultry production. The appropriate amount of feed used at different stages in life of poultry bird determines the level of success and profitability in poultry business. The more the feed is used, the more the poultry bird gains weight. Therefore, 0.30 elasticity of feed input suggest that a 1% increase in feed inputs, would result to an increase of 0.30 percent in the farm output.

The coefficient of **capital input** ($\ln X_4$) was positive and significant at 1% level. The amount of capital inputs per farm determines the level of investment in such farm. High level of investment in poultry business, ceteris paribus, translates to higher returns. Therefore, 0.08 elasticity of capital suggests that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.08 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **farm area** ($\ln X_5$) measured in decimal was positive, which conform to a priori expectation and was significant at 5% level. Therefore, the 0.05 elasticity of **farm size** implies that a 1% increase in farm size, ceteris paribus, would lead to an increase of 0.05 percent in the output of poultry broiler farmers holding other things unchanged.

Table 8: Cobb-Douglas Production Function for Layer

Number of obs =	100			
F(5, 94)	= 98.04		R-squared= 0.839	
Prob > F	= 0.0000		Adj R-squared= 0.819	
$\ln Y_{egg}$	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P>t
$\ln X_1$	0.096	0.024	3.990	0.000
$\ln X_2$	0.267	0.099	2.694	0.008
$\ln X_3$	0.309	0.070	4.395	2.841E-05
$\ln X_4$	0.088	0.015	5.568	0.000
$\ln X_5$	0.050	0.016	3.110	0.003
_cons	0.877	0.234	3.744	0.000
RTS	0.812			

Source: Author's Calculation from the Field Data

Note: Where, $\ln X_1$ = Labor input, $\ln X_2$ = DOC size, $\ln X_3$ = Feed input, $\ln X_4$ = Capital input and $\ln X_5$ = Area of farm

As per the Table 8, the RTS parameter of 0.812 is obtained from the summation of the coefficients of the estimated inputs involved in production process. Thus we can say that a 1% increase in factor inputs would increase meat production by 0.812%. That is, a unit increase in inputs would lead to increase in production, however, not at an equal rate as the input increase. Table 116 below shows the elasticity of production and corresponding Return to Scale (RTS)

3.3 Determinants of Technical Efficiency

3.3.1 Inefficiency Determinants for Broiler

The inefficiency model in table 120 gives some insights on factors affecting technical efficiency.

There was a negative sign before most of the variables explained below in table 5. all these parameter estimates were significantly different from zero at the level of significance of 99% and 95% respectively. The coefficients on gender, ownership of farm were also negative but not significantly different from zero. The negative sign on all these variables means an increase in the variables decreases technical deficiency conversely increases technical efficiency (TE).

The estimated coefficient of **farming experience (Z_1)** was negative and significant at 0.01 significant level. This indicates that farmers with more years of farming experience is in poultry production are relatively more efficient in poultry production and vice versa improves. Farm revenue in poultry production improves with years of farming experience. The more the farmers stay in poultry farming business, the more they get acquainted with the risk elements and ways of mitigating possible losses through them. The new entrants into the business incur a lot of losses through birds mortality and morbidity due to inexperience. Therefore, 0.36 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.36 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **age (Z_2)** of the farmers was estimated to be negative as expected and significant at 0.01 significant levels. The implication is that other farmers were more technically efficient in broiler poultry production than younger ones i.e. older farmers are more technically efficient than younger ones. It is said that the older the farmer, the more experienced he or she will be. Besides, given the importance and significance of land, labor, capital and other resources in farm production, it could be argued that young farmers are deficient in utilization of resources and might not be able to apply inputs or implement certain agro economic practices sufficiently quickly. As timely application of inputs and implementation of management is expected to enhance efficiency, young farmers may find this challenging.

The estimated coefficient of **education variable (Z_3)** was estimated to be negative as expected and significant at 0.01 significant levels. The implication is that poultry farmers with more years of schooling tend to be more efficient in poultry production, presumably due to their enhanced ability to acquire technical knowledge, which makes them more close to the frontier output. Farmers with higher education respond readily to the use of improved technologies, thus producing closer to the frontier. Therefore, 0.40 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.40 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **household size variable (Z_4)** was negative and statistically significant at 0.01 significant levels. This suggests that farmers who have more people i.e. family members in their households tend to be more efficient in poultry production. More adults in family members mean more labor force and thus saving in labor costs. Therefore, 0.25 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.25 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **training** (Z_5) was negative and statistically significant at 0.01 significant levels. This suggests that farmers who receive training tend to be more efficient in poultry production. Therefore, 0.39 elasticity of training variable suggests that a 1% increase in training would result to an increase of 0.39 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **access to credit variable** (Z_6) was estimated to be negative and significant at 0.05 significant levels. This implies that farmers, who have greater access to credit, tend to be more efficient in poultry production. Availability of credit helps increase farm size and provides adequate production and maintenance inputs. Therefore, 0.18 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.18 percent in the farm output. It implies that a well-structured and supervised credit programme or facilities have to be put in place with easy access to monitor and ensure that credit received by the farmers are properly managed and not diverted to other unproductive ventures.

The estimated coefficient for **extension visit variable** (Z_7) was negative and significant at 0.01 significant levels. This implies that farmers, who had more extension visits and teachings, tend to be more efficient in poultry production. Extension visit is very necessary in poultry farming because it affords the farmers the opportunity to learn improved technologies, new techniques of farming and how to acquire needed inputs and services. Therefore, 0.07 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.07 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **location variable** (Z_8) was negative and significant at 0.05 significant levels. The negative sign on the parameter for location implies that farms that are further away from the city or urban area or located at rural area tend to have a lower technical efficiency.

The estimated coefficient for **poultry occupation** (Z_9) was negative and not significant at 0.01 or 0.05 significant levels. May be it's because the types of poultry occupation is not a matter of great concern. Poultry is an activity that can be conducted side by side other agricultural or even non-agricultural work. Poultry production does not require full time effort. This is an important reason because of the rising popularity of poultry business among people.

The estimated coefficient of **married variable** (Z_{10}) was negative and significant at 0.05 significant level. Thus married farmers tended to be more technically efficient, probably reflecting more availability of labor, which is consistent with larger families having more labor at their disposal, thus contributing to higher TE. Therefore, 0.03 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.03 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **membership of association** (Z_{11}) was negative but insignificant. Though the negative sign on the parameter implies that membership of farmers association may lower technical inefficiency, the result is not significant. That is membership of farmers association does not play pivotal role in case of poultry efficiency.

The estimated coefficient for **ownership of the farm** (Z_{12}) was negative but insignificant.

Besides, the value of the estimated coefficient is very negligible. That is types of ownership of the farm do not affect poultry efficiency. Whether sole proprietorship or partnership does not affect poultry production efficiency.

The estimated coefficient for **gender** (Z_{13}) was negative but insignificant. The negative sign implies female farmers tend to have higher technical efficiency than their male counterparts.

The estimated coefficient for **regular medication input** (Z_{14}) was positive and statistically significant at 0.01 significant level. Poultry production involves high level risks, because the birds are susceptible to various diseases and pests attack. To minimize or eradicate these, drugs have to be provided. Also certain drugs are needed in their ration to improve their growth and performance. So the appropriate amount of these drugs used determines the level of success and profitability in poultry business. .therefore, 0.41 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.41 percent in the farm output.

Table 9: Estimated Determinants of Technical Inefficiency for Broiler

Variable	Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Err.	Z	P[Z >z]
Farming experience in poultry production(in Years)	Z1	-0.367	0.080	-4.589	0.000
Age of the farmers	Z2	-0.022	0.007	-3.135	0.001
Level of Education	Z3	-0.409	0.092	-4.436	0.000
Family size	Z4	-0.256	0.041	-6.200	0.000
Training on poultry	Z5	-0.398	0.145	-2.748	0.005
Access to credit facility	Z6	-0.186	0.092	-2.027	0.042
Meeting with Extension agent/govt. agency	Z7	-0.070	0.019	-3.725	0.000
Location of farm	Z8	-0.097	0.044	-2.197	0.028
Types of poultry occupation	Z9	-0.016	0.009	-1.778	0.075
Marital status	Z10	-0.034	0.017	-1.946	0.041
Membership of farmers Association/Cooperative society	Z11	-0.029	0.019	-1.507	0.131
Ownership of the farm	Z12	0.001	0.001	1.24	0.214
Gender	Z13	-0.042	0.021	-1.995	0.054
Regular Medication/ Vaccination facilities	Z14	-0.418	0.145	-2.886	0.005
Constant	Z0	1.613	0.156	10.326	0.000
Diagnostic statistics					
sigma ²		0.79	0.092	8.571	
gamma		0.898	0.253	3.541	
Log Likelihood		-19.891	1.998	-9.954	
Mean TE		0.56			
No. of Observation		100			

Source: Author's Calculation

Notes: Training on poultry: Yes=1;No=0; Access to credit facility: Yes=1;No=0; Meeting with Extension agent/govt. agency: Yes=1;No=0; Location of farm: Urban=1;Rural=0; Types of poultry occupation: Main=1;Part time=0; Marital status: Married=1;Unamrried=0;Yes=1; Membership of farmers Association/Cooperative society Yes=1;No=0; Ownership of the farm:

Sole proprietor=0,Partnership=1; Gender: Female=1;Male=0; Regular Medication/Vaccination facilities: Yes=1;No=0;

DIAGNOSTIC STATISTICS:

The total variance value of sigma square is 0.79 which is highly significant. This result indicated a good fit and the correctness of the specified distribution assumption of the composite error term. Furthermore, a high value of the natural log for the likelihood functions (-19.89), which is always negative, means the observed results were more likely to occur, again implying a high predictive ability of the model.

The value of Gamma (0.898) measures the relationship between random variation in the production of meat and inefficiency in the use of inputs. The computed value of 0.898 implies that 89% of the random variation in broiler production is explained by inefficiency in resource utilization. This implies that the OLS estimates will not be adequate to explain the inefficiencies on poultry broiler farming. Hence the specification of a stochastic frontier production function is therefore justified.

The mean TE was 0.56 (56%), implying that the farmers were not fully efficient as the observed output was 44% less than the maximum output.

3.3.2 *Inefficiency Determinants for Layer*

The estimated coefficient of **farming experience** (Z_1) was negative and significant at 0.01 significant level. This indicates that farmers with more years of farming experience is in poultry production are relatively more efficient in poultry production and vice versa improves. Thus, 0.41 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.41 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **age** (Z_2) of the farmers was estimated to be negative as expected and significant at 0.01 significant levels. The implication is that other farmers were more technically efficient in broiler poultry production than younger ones.

The estimated coefficient of **education variable** (Z_3) was estimated to be negative as expected and significant at 0.01 significant levels. Farmers with higher education respond readily to the use of improved technologies, thus producing closer to the frontier. Thus, 0.35 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.35 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **household size variable** (Z_4) was negative and statistically significant at 0.01 significant levels. This suggests that farmers who have more family members in their households tend to be more efficient in poultry production. Thus 0.31 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.31 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **training** (Z_5) was negative and statistically significant at 0.01 significant levels. This suggests that farmers who receive training tend to be more efficient in poultry production. Therefore, 0.45 elasticity of training variable suggests that a 1% increase in training would result to an increase of 0.45 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **access to credit variable (Z_6)** was estimated to be negative and significant at 0.05 significant levels. This implies that farmers, who have greater access to credit, tend to be more efficient in poultry production. Thus, 0.21 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.21 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **extension visit variable (Z_7)** was negative and significant at 0.01 significant levels. This implies that farmers, who had more extension visits and teachings, tend to be more efficient in poultry production. Therefore, 0.10 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.10 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **location variable (Z_8)** was negative and significant at 0.05 significant levels. The negative sign on the parameter for location implies that farms that are further away from the city or urban area or located at rural area tend to have a lower technical efficiency.

The estimated coefficient for **poultry occupation (Z_9)** was negative and not significant at 0.05 significant levels. Poultry is an activity that can be conducted side by side other agricultural or even non-agricultural work. Poultry production does not require full time effort. This is an important reason because of the rising popularity of poultry business among people.

The estimated coefficient of **married variable (Z_{10})** was negative and not significant at 0.05 significant level. Thus married farmers tended to be more technically efficient. Thus, 0.05 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs would result to an increase of 0.05 percent in the farm output.

The estimated coefficient for **membership of association (Z_{11})** was negative but insignificant. Though the negative sign on the parameter implies that membership of farmers association may lower technical inefficiency, the value of coefficient is very negligible.

The estimated coefficient for **ownership of the farm (Z_{12})** was negative but insignificant. Besides, the value of the estimated coefficient is very small. That is types of ownership of the farm do not affect poultry efficiency.

The estimated coefficient for **gender (Z_{13})** was negative and insignificant. The negative sign implies female farmers tend to have higher technical efficiency than their male counterparts.

The estimated coefficient for **regular medication input (Z_{14})** was negative and statistically significant at 0.01 significant level. Thus, 0.50 elasticity of capital suggest that a 1% increase in capital inputs, would result to an increase of 0.50 percent in the farm output.

Table 10: Estimated Determinants of Technical Inefficiency for Layer

Variable	Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Err.	Z	P[Z >z]
Farming experience in poultry production (in Years)	Z1	-0.410	0.120	-3.413	0.000
Age of the farmers	Z2	-0.050	0.014	-3.558	0.001
Level of Education	Z3	-0.351	0.081	-4.328	0.000
Family size	Z4	-0.312	0.132	-2.358	0.000
Training on poultry	Z5	-0.458	0.123	-3.727	0.005
Access to credit facility	Z6	-0.217	0.078	-2.758	0.042
Meeting with Extension agent/govt. agency	Z7	-0.100	0.036	-2.800	0.000
Location of farm	Z8	-0.079	0.035	-2.256	0.028
Types of poultry occupation	Z9	-0.009	0.005	-1.957	0.075
Marital status	Z10	-0.054	0.012	-4.458	0.051
Membership of farmers Association/Cooperative society	Z11	-0.018	0.015	-1.235	0.131
Ownership of the farm	Z12	0.001	0.002	0.480	0.214
Gender	Z13	-0.059	0.031	-1.910	0.054
Regular Medication/Vaccination facilities	Z14	-0.500	0.116	-4.292	0.005
Constant	Z0	1.003	0.044	22.688	0.000
Diagnostic statistics					
sigma ²		0.63	0.086	7.311	
gamma		0.855	0.398	2.145	
Log Likelihood		-28.771	1.543	-18.64	
Mean TE		0.67			
No. of Observation		100			

Source: Author's Calculation

DIAGNOSTIC STATISTICS

The total variance value of sigma square is 0.63 which is highly significant. This result indicated a good fit and the correctness of the specified distribution assumption of the composite error term. Furthermore, a high value of the natural log for the likelihood functions (-28.77), which is always negative, means the observed results were more likely to occur, again implying a high predictive ability of the model.

The value of Gamma (0.85) measures the relationship between random variation in the production of meat and inefficiency in the use of inputs. The computed value of 0.85 implies that 60% of the random variation in broiler production is explained by inefficiency in resource utilization. This implies that the OLS estimates will not be adequate to explain the inefficiencies on poultry broiler farming. Hence the specification of a stochastic frontier production function is therefore justified.

The mean TE was 0.67 (67%), implying that the farmers were not fully efficient as the observed output was 33% less than the maximum output.

3.4 Hypothesis Test for Broiler Model Specification

Table 11: Hypothesis Test for Broiler Model Specification and Statistical Assumptions

Hypothesis	Likelihood ratio	χ^2	P value	Decision
1. $H_0: \hat{\sigma}^2=0$	35.89	13.71	0.008	Reject H_0
2. No inefficiency effect [$H_0: Z_0=Z_1=Z_2=Z_3=Z_4=Z_5=... Z_{14}=0$]	39.713	18.91	0.000	Reject H_0
Inefficiency effects in the stochastic production function are not stochastic				
3. No effects of inefficiency factors included in the inefficiency model [$H_0: Z_1=Z_2=Z_3=Z_4=Z_5=... Z_{14}=0$]	27.658	16.88	0.002	Reject H_0
4. $H_0: \mu=0$	21.88	17.83	0.001	Reject H_0

Source: Author's Calculation

Hypothesis 1, which specified that the inefficiency effects were not stochastic, was strongly rejected. This implied that the traditional average response function was not a satisfactory depiction for poultry broiler production, given the specification of the stochastic production frontier and inefficiency models in equations.

Hypothesis 2 was regarding the existence of inefficiency factor ($H_0: Z_0=Z_1=Z_2=Z_3=Z_4=Z_5=... Z_{14}=0$). Here the null hypothesis was rejected at 1% level which implied that in the model the inefficiency was present i.e. the inefficiency effects in the model are stochastic.

Hypothesis 3, which specified that the explanatory variables in the model for the inefficiency factors had zero coefficients, was hereby rejected at 1% significant level.

Hypothesis 4 (i.e. $\mu=0$) explored that each farm was operating on the technically efficient frontier and that the systematic and random efficiency in the inefficiency effects were zero. This was rejected in favor of the occurrence of inefficiency effects.

Hypothesis Test for Layer Model Specification

Table 12: Hypothesis Test for Layer Model Specification and Statistical Assumptions

Hypothesis	Likelihood ratio	χ^2	P value	Decision
1. $H_0: \hat{\sigma}^2=0$	47.79	17.71	0.001	Reject H_0
2. No inefficiency effect [$H_0: Z_0=Z_1=Z_2=Z_3=Z_4=Z_5=\dots Z_{14}=0$]	35.51	25.73	3.6E-05	Reject H_0
Inefficiency effects in the stochastic production function are not stochastic				
3. No effects of inefficiency factors included in the inefficiency model [$H_0: Z_1=Z_2=Z_3=Z_4=Z_5=\dots Z_{14}=0$]	29.858	19.89	0.000	Reject H_0
4. $H_0: \mu=0$	31.58	27.33	1.7E-05	Reject H_0

Source: Author's Calculation

In case of layer also we get the similar result. Hypothesis 1, which specifies that the inefficiency effects are not stochastic, was strongly rejected.

Hypothesis 2 was also rejected. This stated that the inefficiency effects are absent from the model (i.e. $H_0: Z_0=Z_1=Z_2=Z_3=Z_4=Z_5=\dots Z_{14}=0$). Here the null hypothesis was rejected at 1% level which implies that in the model the inefficiency was present.

Hypothesis 3 was rejected as well at 1% significant level. This implies that the explanatory variables in the model contributed significantly to the explanation of efficiency in poultry egg production in sample area.

Finally hypothesis 4 explores that each farm is operating on the technically efficient frontier and that the systematic and random efficiency in the inefficiency effects are zero. This was rejected in favor of the presence of inefficiency effects.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this study technical inefficiency of poultry broiler and layer farms of Bangladesh has been estimated by using the stochastic frontier method. The results of the study give information to policy makers on how to better aim efforts to improve poultry farm efficiency. From the study we observe that large farms were more technically efficient than medium farms and medium farms were more than that of small. This supports the theory that large farms exhibits many types of economies such as economies of scale, economies of management and operation and economies of buying (inputs)and selling(output) etc. Due to the least per unit cost, reduced managerial cost in long run large farms face more efficiency than do medium and small farms. Conversely, the smaller the farm the lesser the efficiency is (at least as per as the present study). The smallholder broiler farmers are characterized by poor production process, low production quantities thus slow growth. That's why small farms (and medium farms also) demand special nursing and policy support from the govt. to lift up the efficiency. We need to keep in mind that small scale poultry enterprise play pivotal role for rural people especially illiterate, women and youth through generating employment opportunity. Small poultry farms demand special nursing and policy support from the govt. to lift up the efficiency. We need to keep in mind that poultry especially small scale poultry enterprise play pivotal role for rural people especially illiterate, women and youth through generating employment opportunity. And small farm in this sector can reduce the rate of poverty enormously. At the same time, locating technical

efficiency of large farms below the frontier indicates more capability to develop in future by adopting appropriate management practices. The heterogeneity in management and production practices applied by farmers with varying socio-economic state may clarify the distribution of technical efficiency.

The long-term position of Bangladesh as a prominent producer of poultry products leftovers bright even after the bird flu epidemic that has held off its prospect. The swelling demand for poultry meat and eggs has improved poultry activity into a full-grown industry from a mere household activity until recently. The poultry industry has immense potential for boosting the economic growth of the country as well as ensuring food security. Agricultural land is limited and is reducing day by day. A solution to the issue of farmland depletion could be formulation of a sensible and realistic land-use policy. Poultry is most probably the only sector that can grow vertically and produce maximum amount of eggs and chicken meat using the minimum land. Rising population and moderate growth of per capita income, urbanization and high income elasticity of demand, are likely to bring an enormous increase in the demand for poultry products. This is the high time for govt. to take all necessary policy steps regarding poultry sector particularly emphasizing on the availability of quality chicks and feed, vaccination service by dept. of livestock, tax exemption and providing subsidy, introducing poultry insurance and finally creating a poultry friendly environment. All categories of stakeholders should partake in policy formulation for the development of the poultry industry. The sector will contribute more than it is expected to be if proper policy is taken and will contribute to the country's GDP leading a strong domestic economy of the country.

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